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Improving Primary Students' Literacy Through International Assessment Programs

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Abstract: *This article refers to the reforms taking place in our education system and, through this, being among the developed countries. Teaching STEM subjects in schools, international evaluation programs are gaining importance in improving the literacy of high and elementary school students.*

Keywords: *quality of education, PIRLS, TIMSS, literacy, research, respondent, reading*

Introduction

Today, the education system requires rapid development based on social processes. Through education, a new generation capable of fulfilling future tasks will be formed in the society. Taking this into account, there is a need to strengthen the material and technical base of general education schools and pre-school educational institutions, to increase attention to comprehensive education of the young generation through modern social innovations.

At a time when society is changing and developing very rapidly, its level of development depends on the quality of education. As the President noted: "Today, when our country has entered a new period of its development, large-scale changes are being implemented in all areas. The success of these reforms, our country's taking a worthy place among the developed, modern countries of the world, first of all, is inextricably linked with the development of the field of science and education, and with our ability to compete on a global scale in this regard..." - says Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in order to raise the quality of education to a high level in accordance with the requirements of reforms in the social and economic spheres based on the requirements of the times, as well as to further improve the control of the quality of education in the continuous education system,

and to implement the state policy in the field of control of the objective assessment of the effectiveness of the educational process. In his address to the Oliy Majlis, among the urgent issues of state and society importance, he highlighted the issue of improving the quality of education, "preparation for the international assessment processes in 2021", and now a lot of work is being done in this regard. In particular, in order to improve the quality of education and provide students with modern knowledge, the Ministry of Public Education is working on creating a modern national educational program based on advanced foreign experience. Textbooks with modern design and content are being gradually developed based on the national education program. In this direction, it is planned to spread the experience of presidential schools in teaching STEAM subjects, participate in international evaluation programs aimed at determining the literacy and knowledge levels of students in the world, and various reforms are being implemented in order to raise the indicators of Uzbek youth to a high level in this program.

In particular, the quality, level and level of education in the world, such as PISA (International Program for Assessment of Student Achievement), PIRLS (International Study of Reading and Comprehension), TIMSS (researcher of the quality of mathematics and concrete sciences at school) there are a number of international studies, which are widely used as a criterion for improving the quality of education in developed countries. As the first steps, it can be said that international experiences on the introduction of international research were studied, about 30 responsible employees were trained in foreign countries, 7 international experts were involved, and 260 trainers were trained across the country. In particular, the PISA program evaluates the literacy of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences, not only the fact that they remember information from curricula and textbooks within these subjects, but also their ability to find optimal solutions to various situations in everyday life, as well as creative and creative thinking skills. PISA focuses on the creative thinking processes that can reasonably be expected of fifteen-year-old students. Its purpose is not to identify highly creative individuals, but to analyze how creatively students can think in expressing and defining ideas, and how this skill, in turn, is related to the learning process, school activities, and other aspects of the educational system. In the PIRLS program, the ability of 4th-grade students to quickly read traditional texts, but also to understand and interpret texts given outside the textbook, and to express their thoughts in written language is evaluated. In short, the results of international studies show how well our young people are prepared for life and how well the educational programs offered to them meet today's demands.

The purpose of the PIRLS study is to compare reading comprehension levels of fourth grade students from different countries around the world, as well as to identify differences in reading literacy across national education systems. According to the international dictionary of research, "reader's literacy" is the ability of a person to understand and make sense of various written languages necessary to fully express himself in life and achieve his goals.

PIRLS research aims to solve the following problems:

- development of objective measures and tools reflecting world priorities in the field of education;
- comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of the organization of the country's educational process;
- identification of contextual factors that influenced the research results;
- having evidence-based information recognized by the international community.

The object of the study is the educational achievements of primary school graduates, as it collects all the knowledge and skills of teaching in the fourth academic year. At this age, students should be well versed in reading so that they can use a variety of texts in content and format to continue successfully in mainstream school. PIRLS will be held according to the plan of the International Center.

Countries with large territories are divided into layers corresponding to administrative divisions. In order to select strata, data on the number of students in the studied population are collected in each region. It is carried out by a probabilistic method, taking into account the number of students, by selecting schools in all countries. Selection of research participants is carried out in several stages. In the first stage, the national coordinators of the participating countries send the lists of all schools (city, village, village) in the country to the International Coordination Center. About 150 schools from each country are then selected using a special program using the "random number method". Schools selected by international experts to participate in the study provide the National Coordinator with lists of fourth-grade students in full correspondence with classroom data. The list of 4th grade students is entered into the database and sent to the International Coordination Center. Studying PIRLS is carried out in strict accordance with the guidelines and rules developed by a single center for standardization of reading technology in all countries participating in the project. Every step of the research—sampling, translation and adaptation, testing and interrogation, data validation and processing—is overseen by international experts. For example, translations of test items and questionnaires of respondents were sent to international experts for further verification. In each region, the National Coordinator coordinates with the regional Education Directorate with the Regional Coordinating Center responsible for organizing and conducting the research. Accordingly, a school coordinator will be assigned to each school selected for the study. The test taker is selected from among experienced professional teachers who do not teach in the tested classroom and school. During the testing process, international observers are divided into selected schools. They are appointed by the International Association for Academic Performance Assessment (IAPA) from among independent experts in the field of education of the participating country (they may be representatives of international and non-governmental organizations). The appointed observer in Uzbekistan is required to speak Uzbek, Russian and English. According to the specific requirements developed, the International Observer will personally select a certain number of schools to participate. This ensures the objectivity of the study results.

In short, the effectiveness of the modernization of Uzbek education, which is carried out in order to improve the quality of education and the possibilities of their use, depends to a large extent on the level of use of objective data obtained in the framework of research on various types of educational results. All these studies provide information on the state of education and trends in its change, allow to correlate the planned and achieved results, compare the quality of education with other countries of the world, and identify the most important problems that need to be solved on this basis. The results of these studies serve as guidelines for changing the direction of ongoing reforms and forecasting the state of education in the coming years.

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